

Reproducibility Experimental Results - Random Sampling Plus Fake Data: Multidimensional Frequency Estimates With Local Differential Privacy

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 About the paper

Using Local differential privacy (LDP) users can privatize their data before transmitting it to the server. When collecting data there are two components the client side and the aggregator (e.g. the server which collects the data from multiple sources). The paper [1] proposes a method that answers the question: For the same privacy budget, is there a solution for multidimensional frequency estimates that provides better data utility than data Splitting and more protection than Sampling? What if the sampling result (i.e., the selected attribute) was not disclosed with the aggregator?

The paper proposes a solution called Random Sampling Plus Fake Data which allows creating uncertainty over the sampled attribute by generating fake data for each non-sampled attribute. With RS+FD, the client-side has two steps: local randomization and fake data generation. First, an LDP mechanism preserves privacy for the data of the sampled attribute. Second, the fake data generator provides fake data for each non-sampled attribute. This way, the privatized data is "hidden" among fake data and, hence, the sampling result is not disclosed along with the users' report (and statistics) [1]

1.2 Overview of the RS+FD algorithm

1.2.1 Basic RS+FD. We consider the local DP model, in which there are two entities, namely, users and the aggregator (an untrusted curator). Let n be the total number of users, A be the total number of attributes, $k = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_d]$ be the domain size of each attribute, A be a local randomizer, and " ϵ " be the privacy budget.

Each user holds a tuple $v = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_d)$, i.e., a private value per attribute.

The **client-side** is split into two steps, namely, local randomization and fake data generation (cf. Fig. 1)

Initially, each user samples a unique attribute j uniformly at random and applies an LDP mechanism to its value v_j . Indeed, RS+FD is generic to be applied with any existing LDP mechanisms. Next, for each $d-1$ non-sampled attribute i , the user generates one random fake data. Finally, each user sends the (LDP or fake) value of each attribute to the aggregator, i.e., a tuple $y = (1, 2, \dots,)$. This way, the sampling result is not disclosed with the aggregator. In summary, Alg. 1 exhibits the pseudocode of our RS+FD solution.

Aggregator. For each attribute $j \in [1, d]$, the aggregator performs frequency (or histogram) estimation on the collected data by removing bias introduced by the local randomizer and fake data.

Limitations. Similar to other sampling-based methods for collecting multidimensional data under LDP [17, 34, 40, 46], our RS+FD solution also entails sampling error, which is due to observing a sample instead of the entire population.

1.2.2 RS+FD with GRR. Client side. Integrating GRR as the local randomizer A into Alg. 1 (RS+FD[GRR]) requires no modification. Initially, on the clientside, each user randomly samples an attribute j . Next, the value v_j is privatized with GRR using the size of the domain k_j and the privacy parameter ϵ . In addition, for each non-sampled $d-1$ attribute i , the user also generates fake data uniformly at random according to the domain size k_i . Lastly, the user transmits the privatized tuple y , which includes the LDP value of the true data "hidden" among fake data.

Fig. 1. Overview of the RS+FD solution [1]

Algorithm 1 Random Sampling plus Fake Data (RS+FD)

Input : tuple $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_d)$, domain size of attributes $\mathbf{k} = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_d]$, privacy parameter ϵ , local randomizer \mathcal{A} .
Output : privatized tuple $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_d)$.

- 1: $\epsilon' = \ln(d \cdot (e^\epsilon - 1) + 1)$ ▷ amplification by sampling [31]
- 2: $j \leftarrow \text{Uniform}(\{1, 2, \dots, d\})$ ▷ Selection of attribute to privatize
- 3: $B_j \leftarrow v_j$
- 4: $y_j \leftarrow \mathcal{A}(B_j, k_j, \epsilon')$ ▷ privatize data of the sampled attribute
- 5: **for** $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, d\} / j$ **do** ▷ non-sampled attributes
- 6: $y_i \leftarrow \text{Uniform}(\{1, \dots, k_i\})$ ▷ generate fake data
- 7: **end for**

return : $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_d)$ ▷ sampling result is not disclosed

Fig. 2. Algorithm 1. RS+FD [1]

Aggregator RS+FD[GRR]. On the server-side, for each attribute $j \in [1, d]$, the aggregator estimates $f(v_i)$ for the frequency of each value $i \in [1, d]$ as:

$$\hat{f}(v_i) = \frac{N_i d k_j - n(d - 1 + q k_j)}{n k_j (p - q)}$$

1.2.3 RS+FD with OUE. Client side. To use UE-based protocols (OUE in our work) as local randomizer \mathcal{A} in Alg. 1, there is, first, a need to define the fake data generation procedure. We propose two solutions: RS+FD[OUE-z] in Alg. 2, which applies OUE to $d-1$ zero-vectors, and RS+FD[OUE-r] in Alg. 3, which applies OUE to $d-1$ one-hot-encoded fake data (uniform at random). We note that, on the one hand, introducing fake data through privatizing zero-vectors introduces less noise as there is only one parameter to perturb each bit, i.e., $\Pr[0 \rightarrow 1] = q$. On the other hand, starting with zero-vectors may not suffice to "hide" the sampled attribute if the perturbation probability q is too small. Studying this effect is out of the scope of this paper and is left as future work.

Aggregator RS+FD[OUE-z]. On the server-side, if fake data are generated with OUE applied to zero-vectors, as in Alg. 2, for each attribute $j \in [1, d]$, the aggregator estimates $f(v_i)$ for the frequency of each value $i \in [1, k_j]$ as:

$$\hat{f}(v_i) = \frac{d(N_i - nq)}{n(p - q)}$$

Algorithm 2 RS+FD[OUE-z]

Input : tuple $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_d)$, domain size of attributes $\mathbf{k} = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_d]$, privacy parameter ϵ , local randomizer OUE.
Output : privatized tuple $\mathbf{B}' = (B'_1, B'_2, \dots, B'_d)$.

1:	$\epsilon' = \ln(d \cdot (e^\epsilon - 1) + 1)$	▶ amplification by sampling [31]
2:	$j \leftarrow \text{Uniform}(\{1, 2, \dots, d\})$	▶ Selection of attribute to privatize
3:	$B_j = \text{Encode}(v_j) = [0, 0, \dots, 1, 0, \dots, 0]$	▶ one-hot-encoding
4:	$B'_j \leftarrow \text{OUE}(B_j, \epsilon')$	▶ privatize real data with OUE
5:	for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, d\} / j$ do	▶ non-sampled attributes
6:	$B_i \leftarrow [0, 0, \dots, 0]$	▶ initialize zero-vectors
7:	$B'_i \leftarrow \text{OUE}(B_i, \epsilon')$	▶ randomize zero-vector with OUE
8:	end for	
	return : $\mathbf{B}' = (B'_1, B'_2, \dots, B'_d)$	▶ sampling result is not disclosed

Fig. 3. Algorithm 2. RS+FD[OUE-z] [1]

Aggregator RS+FD[OUE-r]. Otherwise, if fake data are generated with OUE applied to one-hot-encoded random data, as in Alg. 3, for each attribute $j \in [1, d]$, the aggregator estimates $f(v_i)$ for the frequency of each value $i \in [1, k_j]$ as:

$$\hat{f}(v_i) = \frac{N_i dk_j - n [qk_j + (p - q)(d - 1) + qk_j(d - 1)]}{nk_j(p - q)}$$

Algorithm 3 RS+FD[OUE-r]

Input : tuple $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_d)$, domain size of attributes $\mathbf{k} = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_d]$, privacy parameter ϵ , local randomizer OUE.
Output : privatized tuple $\mathbf{B}' = (B'_1, B'_2, \dots, B'_d)$.

1:	$\epsilon' = \ln(d \cdot (e^\epsilon - 1) + 1)$	▶ amplification by sampling [31]
2:	$j \leftarrow \text{Uniform}(\{1, 2, \dots, d\})$	▶ Selection of attribute to privatize
3:	$B_j = \text{Encode}(v_j) = [0, 0, \dots, 1, 0, \dots, 0]$	▶ one-hot-encoding
4:	$B'_j \leftarrow \text{OUE}(B_j, \epsilon')$	▶ privatize real data with OUE
5:	for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, d\} / j$ do	▶ non-sampled attributes
6:	$y_i \leftarrow \text{Uniform}(\{1, \dots, k_i\})$	▶ generate fake data
7:	$B_i \leftarrow \text{Encode}(y_i)$	▶ one-hot-encoding
8:	$B'_i \leftarrow \text{OUE}(B_i, \epsilon')$	▶ randomize fake data with OUE
9:	end for	
	return : $\mathbf{B}' = (B'_1, B'_2, \dots, B'_d)$	▶ sampling result is not disclosed

Fig. 4. Algorithm 3. RS+FD[OUE-r] [1]

1.2.4 Analytical analysis: RS+FD with ADP. In a multidimensional setting with different domain sizes for each attribute, a dynamic selection of LDP mechanisms is preferred. Because our estimators are unbiased, their variance is equal to the mean squared error (MSE) that is commonly used in practice as an accuracy metric. In this work, we analyze the approximate variances VAR1 for RS+FD[GRR] and VAR2 for RS+FD[OUE-z], in which $f(v_i) =$

0. This is, first, because under the local model of DP, the real frequency $f(v_i)$ is unknown and, second, because in real life the vast majority of values appear very infrequently. This method is a dynamic selection between RS+FD[GRR] and RS+FD[OUE-z] based on variance. [1]

1.3 Experiments described in the paper

The paper describes two main experiments: one experiment on synthetic data and another experiment on real world data. The distribution of values in each attribute follows an uniform distribution, for all synthetic datasets. The four real-world datasets with non-uniform distributions used in the second experiments are Nursery, Adult, MS-FIMU, Census-Income, which are all from the UCI machine learning repository. As an evaluation metric, the Mean Squared Error averaged per number of attributes is used. [1]

2 EXPERIMENTS DESCRIPTION

In this chapter we will describe the experiments that we ran to test the reproducibility of the original paper.

2.1 Platform and libraries

We setup the docker with different platforms (Windows and Ubuntu Linux) to see if the results differ. For this experiment we ran the original algorithms in the setting provided by the authors. This did not produce any difference in the results.

In the paper authors fixed environmental factors: python version (3.8.5), numpy version (1.19.5) and numba version (0.53.1). We decided to vary the versions of other libraries used in the original code (pandas, scipy, scikit-learn) limited by the compatibility with provided libraries versions. In this experiment we also proved the reproducibility of the paper.

2.2 Privacy budget

We decided to vary algorithms' parameters used by the authors. The reasoning for setting privacy budget (denoted ϵ) was not provided, although [2] and [3] were referenced. We, therefore, ran our experiments with 3 privacy budget ranges - from the original paper and from two other papers. We encountered the challenges described in the following chapter, but they did not influence the reproducibility of the original paper.

2.3 Datasets

We decided to vary random seeds for synthetic data creation. As the paper focuses on the relative change in accuracy and not on the absolute values produced, that way we could check if the behaviour of the algorithms changes for different data. We carried out the experiments with different privacy budget range to ensure the stibility of the result. No reproducibility issues were found during these experiments.

2.4 Running the algorithms

Another part of our research was devoted to running the algorithms provided by the authors with different random seed sets from those defined by the authors. In the original paper the authors varied random seeds from 0 to 100, sequentially. We ran the experiments with ranges from 101 to 200 with step 1, from 0 to 500 with step 5 and for 100 random seeds generated with fixed random seed 42.

3 CHALLENGES IN REPRODUCTION

3.1 Small epsilon values

While describing the experimental setup the authors did not give a clear reason why they use a specific range for the privacy budget parameter ϵ . Their reasoning was the following: "We vary the privacy parameter in a

logarithmic range ..., which is within range of values experimented in the literature for multidimensional data (e.g., in [2] the range is $\epsilon = [0.5, \dots, 4]$ and in [3] the range is $\epsilon = [0.1, \dots, 10]$). In order to ensure that this choice does not affect the result, we experimented with the mentioned ϵ ranges. It is also important to mention that in the mentioned papers the specific reasons for choosing ϵ as well as the step lengths in the specified ranges were also not stated.

During the experiments with SPL algorithm one specific ϵ value (0.1) provided for inconsistently occurring error. In order to understand the reasons for that we varied datasets/set seeds for the whole procedure and the problematic parts. We were able to narrow the problem down to the randomized algorithms UE and GRR. In the end everything came down to transforming NaN values to zeros after randomized procedures, which stabilized the process. For this we use `numpy.nan_to_num` function. The NaN values occurred because with such a small privacy budget parameter in UE procedure the probability of the mean value of the estimations being negative rose and lead to the `ZeroDivisionError`.

This could be looked upon as not a reproducibility issue, but rather an issue with inconsistent choice of parameter range in the area.

4 RESULTS

In this chapter we provide only the part of reproduction results, because varying different factors did not yield significantly different results. In 5 we can see the reproduction results for privacy budget in the range $[0.1, 10]$ with different algorithms. The variance for the runs with is represented by transparent regions.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results generated by reproducing the paper we did not find any differences from the original paper. The python notebooks ran as intended and the results were similar to the ones in the paper regardless of operating system (e.g Windows, Linux). The only issues we encountered are described in the second section of this paper. Other than that the resulting graphs are the same as the ones shown in the original paper.

Fig. 5. Running different algorithms with varied parameters

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